

THE ALKALOID OF *RAUWOLFIA CANESCENS*, LINN. PART III. SOME DEGRADATION PRODUCTS OF RAUWOLSCINE

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Although rauwolscine, $C_{21}H_{26}O_3N_2$, is isomeric with and strikingly similar to yohimbine in its physical, chemical and physiological properties and in most of its degradation products, it differs from yohimbine in some respects. The third oxygen atom in rauwolscine is probably present as a hydroxyl group which is not reactive like that of yohimbine; one of the nitrogen atoms is found to be secondary and the other tertiary and is attached to a ring. A skeletal formula of rauwolscine has been suggested after due considerations of several fragments like harman, 3-ethylindole, indole-2-carboxylic acid and isophthalic acid, isolated and identified from the degradation products of rauwolscine. Rauwolscinic acid does not undergo facile decarboxylation like yohimbic acid.

Rauwolscine, $C_{21}H_{26}O_3N_2$, the major alkaloid of *Rauwolfia canescens* (Mookerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 33) was previously reported to be allied to yohimbine both structurally (Mookerjee, *ibid.*, 1941, 18, 485) and physiologically (Chakravarty, *Science and Culture*, 1941, 7, 458). Like yohimbine it splits up on hydrolysis into methyl alcohol and a monobasic acid, called rauwolscinic acid $C_{20}H_{24}O_3N_2$, isomeric with yohimbic acid.

A comparative study of the absorption curves of both rauwolscine and yohimbine shows that the curves are similar to the curve of indole, pointing to the presence of an indole nucleus in rauwolscine molecule (*loc. cit.*). Yohimbine is known to possess an indole nucleus (Barger and Field, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1025; Warnat, *Ber.*, 1926, 59, 2891; 1927, 60, 1118; Hahn and Just, *Ber.*, 1932, 65, 717; Winterstein and Walter, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1933, 16, 1343). The physical evidence of the presence of the indole nucleus in rauwolscine molecule has been confirmed by a study of some of the degradation products of the alkaloid, described in the present paper. The functions of all nitrogen and oxygen atoms have also been elucidated as far as possible and a skeleton formula has been proposed for the base, rauwolscine.

Rauwolscine with its two nitrogen atoms behaves as a monoacid base yielding a monohydrochloride, $B.HCl$, and an acid oxalate of the formula, $B.H_2C_2O_4$.

Rauwolscine can neither be brominated nor hydrogenated by means of (a) hydriodic acid (sp. gr. 1.7) and red phosphorus, (b) tin and hydrochloric acid, (c) sodium amalgam, and (d) catalytic hydrogenation. These facts indicate absence of unsaturation or of $-N=C-$ linkage in rauwolscine molecule. No definite evidence could be obtained for the presence of a primary nitrogen atom. The iminomethyl determination was absolutely negative. As the absorption spectrum of the base is strongly suggestive of the presence of an indole nucleus, one of the nitrogen atoms must form part of the indole ring and hence does not normally respond to reactions characteristic of $-NH-$ group. This assumption also explains the monoacidic character of rauwolscine. The second nitrogen atom is believed to be a tertiary one and in all probability forms part of a saturated ring or rings. This tertiary nitrogen atom probably accounts for the basic character of rauwolscine, the first nitrogen atom

(or the indole) being very feebly basic. The presence of a $-NH-CO$ group, which may readily explain the almost neutral character of the first nitrogen, is another possibility. But an amido-nitrogen along with the indole skeleton would have rendered rauwolscine far less basic than what it is. A monoacetyl derivative could, however, be obtained from rauwolscine by heating with acetic anhydride and fused sodium acetate. This is very likely *N*-acetyl derivative since indole, harman, harmaline, rutaecarpine and yohimbine etc., are known to yield *N*-acetyl derivatives, under similar conditions.

Two of the three oxygen atoms in rauwolscine molecule are present as carbomethoxy group as has already been proved (*loc. cit.*). The function of the third oxygen atom could not be ascertained easily since rauwolscine does not respond to the tests for aldehyde, ketone and alkyl ethers. No definite proofs for the presence of either alcoholic or phenolic hydroxyl group could be obtained as rauwolscine does not form *O*-methyl, or phthalic acid esters. Rauwolscine could not be converted into a chloro compound with phosphorous pentachloride, or into any unsaturated compound by the elimination of a molecule of water with dehydrating agents. The significance of the acetyl derivative is that it is indicative of the presence of an active hydrogen atom. The determination of active hydrogen in rauwolscine by Zerewitinoff's method shows the presence of two atoms of active hydrogen, one of which is apparently capable of undergoing acetylation. The second active hydrogen may possibly belong to a reactive methylene group, but the failure of rauwolscine and rauwolscinic acid to condense with acetone and anisaldehyde does not lend support to this hypothesis. The only possible way of accounting for this second active hydrogen, therefore, is to assume the presence of a hydroxyl group. These speculations lead one to the probability that rauwolscine contains NH group (as indole residue) and OH (alcoholic) group which, however, is more resistant to reactions than the one present in yohimbine, in as much as the latter yields a sulphuric ester and *O*-acetyl derivative (Barger and Field, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915 107, 1025; 1923, 123, 1038), without any difficulty. The formula of rauwolscine, therefore, can be expanded to :

Pyrolysis of Rauwolscinic Acid.

From the products of pyrolysis of rauwolscinic acid at $300^{\circ}/4.5$ mm., a strong base, m.p. 232° , and a neutral liquid have been isolated in pure condition.

The solid base, which analyses for $C_{12}H_{10}N_2$, shows a pale blue fluorescence in aqueous solution, which deepened on the addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid. It is a monoacidic base, and yields a straw-yellow crystalline hydrochloride, $C_{12}H_{10}N_2 \cdot HCl$, m.p. 276° , (decomp.) and a bright yellow crystalline picrate, $C_{12}H_{10}N_2 \cdot C_6H_5O_7(NO_2)_3$, m.p. $256-58^{\circ}$ (decomp.). The molecular formulae and physical properties of the base and its salts suggest its identity with harman (I),

which is reported to melt at 232°, and produces a straw-coloured crystalline hydrochloride, m.p. 276°, (decomp.) and a bright yellow picrate, m.p. 255° (decomp.).

(I)

(II)

(III)

The identity is definitely established by mixed melting point with an authentic sample of harman prepared by the method of Kermack, Perkin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1617).

The neutral product after final purification by distillation in vacuum is obtained as a mobile, colourless liquid which turns reddish brown in air. It has a faecal odour like skatole and it turns a pine chip soaked in concentrated hydrochloric acid red. It produces ruby red crystalline picrate, m.p. 115-16°.

A comparison between the picrate of 3-ethylindole and that of the neutral liquid has been made, when they are observed to have similar physical properties. Further, no depression of melting point is observed when the two are mixed together. This fact establishes the constitution of the neutral compound as 3-ethylindole (II), which is apparently formed by further breakdown of the harman residue present in rauwolscine.

These degradation products confirm the presence of indole nucleus in rauwolscine and definitely establish not only the nature but also the relative positions of the two nitrogen atoms present in rauwolscine.

One would not, however, be justified to assume that harman molecule as such is present in rauwolscine and it is linked up with the rest of the molecule through a carbon atom of the pyridine nucleus. Such an assumption would not agree with the experimental observations, namely, (i) the production of 3-ethylindole and (ii) the absence of the tendency of rauwolscine to undergo reduction. On the other hand if the pyridine ring in rauwolscine is assumed to be reduced (corresponding to tetrahydroharman) (formula III), the formation of both harman and 3-ethylindole during pyrolysis is readily explained. This part formula is open to objection because of the presence of two $-NH-$ groups which cannot be reconciled with the observation that rauwolscine produces a monoacetyl derivative only. If, however, the assumption is made that union with the rest of the molecule has taken place through the nitrogen atom of the reduced pyridine as in formula (IV), no serious objection can be raised in interpreting the experimental results. Such a part formula would fully explain the differential behaviour of the two nitrogen atoms in rauwolscine, as also its fission into harman and 3-ethylindole. This portion (IV) is analogous to what is present in yohimbine. Accordingly rauwolscinic acid has been fused with solid potassium hydroxide at 300°, when besides harman, two different acids, one free from

(IV)

nitrogen and the other containing nitrogen atom, are isolated from the fusion product.

The nitrogenous acid is obtained after careful purification involving high vacuum sublimation and by crystallisation in the final stages as shining flakes, m. p. 200-201°. The acid, when treated with soda lime, produces an oil. The latter has an offensive odour like skatole and turns pine chip moistened with concentrated hydrochloric acid red. The acid produces a violet-red colouration with isatin and concentrated sulphuric acid. The analytical data of the nitrogenous acid, $C_9H_7NO_2$, agreed with those of indole-monocarboxylic acid. That it is indole-2-carboxylic acid is conclusively proved by comparing it with a synthetic specimen, prepared according to the method of Ciamician and Zetti (*Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1930). There is no depression in mixed melting point and other properties are also found to be identical.

The nitrogen-free acid, after careful purification by repeated sublimation in *vacuo* and at ordinary pressure, is obtained as colourless shining needles, m. p. 328-30° (with sublimation). Its properties and analytical data correspond to those of *isophthalic acid*. The methyl ester of the degradation product melts at 68° and no depression in m. p. is observed when mixed with an authentic specimen of dimethyl ester of *isophthalic acid*, having m. p. 68.5°.

It has already been mentioned that rauwolscine exhibits a striking similarity to yohimbine in its properties both physical and chemical. It is found that rauwolscine resembles too in some of its degradation products with yohimbine and a table comparing their degradation products is drawn up below.

TABLE I.

	Rauwolscine.	Yohimbine.
1. Dry distillation ...	(a) Harman, m. p. 232° (b) 3-Ethylindole $C_{11}H_{11}N$, liquid b. p. 80°/0.1 mm.	(a) Harman, m. p. 232° (b) An unidentified indole derivative, m. p. 56°.
2. Alkali fusion ...	(a) An unidentified indole derivative, liquid (b) Harman, m. p. 232° $C_{11}H_{11}N_2$ (c) Indole-2-carboxylic acid: $C_9H_7NO_2$, m. p. 200-201°. (d) <i>iso</i> Phthalic acid, $C_8H_6O_4$, m. p. 328-30°. (with sublimation).	(a) 3-Ethylindole, m. p. 32°. (b) Tetrahydrobyrrine. $C_{11}H_{13}N_2$, m. p. 167°. (c) Indole-2-carboxylic acid, $C_9H_7NO_2$, m. p. 199-201°. (d) <i>m</i> -Toluic acid, $C_8H_8O_2$, m. p. 110°.

It, therefore, appears that rauwolscine possesses *at least* four rings which correspond to A, B, C and E of yohimbine and the skeletal formula for rauwolscine appears to be (V).

The union of the cycloparaffin ring through the tertiary N atom as shown above is arbitrary, but appears probable in view of the similarity of degradation products obtained both from yohimbine and rauwolscine. Definite proofs for the presence of ring D in rauwolscine skeleton have yet to be obtained and the positions of hydroxyl and carbomethoxy groups have to be discussed. These will be the subject matter of a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acylation of Rauwolscine.—Rauwolscine (0.25 g.) was boiled with acetic anhydride (5 c. c.) and freshly fused sodium acetate (0.25 g.) for 6 hours. The mixture was cooled and poured in a thin stream with constant stirring into ice-cold water (50 c. c.), when a brown, resinous matter separated, and was filtered off. The clear coloured filtrate was made ammoniacal, when the free acylated compound was precipitated; this was taken up in ether (80 c. c.) and the red ethereal solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue on removal of ether was repeatedly crystallised from alcohol when globules of colourless solid, melting at 216-18° with decomposition were obtained. (Found in a specimen dried over P₂O₅, *in vacuo* for 2 hours at 125-30° : OMe, 7.41. C₂₁H₂₃O₃N₂·COCH₃ requires OMe, 7.07 per cent).

Hydrolysis of Monoacetylrauwolscine.—Monoacetylrauwolscine (0.2 g.) was boiled with aqueous sodium hydroxide (5 c. c.; 2*N*) for two hours. The pale red solution, thus obtained, was just acidified with acetic acid (2*N*) and the solid precipitate was collected, washed with ice-cold water and dried. The solid was then esterified with methyl alcohol and hydrogen chloride and kept overnight. Colourless needles separating were collected, dissolved in warm water, cooled in ice and made alkaline with liquor ammonia. Solids precipitated were crystallised from alcohol when they melted at 232° (decomp.) and showed no change in m. p. when mixed with rauwolscine.

Determination of Active Hydrogen in Rauwolscine.

The Zerewitinoff determination on a semi-micro scale by a modified apparatus of Flaschenträger gave the following consistent results:

- (a) 0.0623 g. of rauwolscine in 2 c. c. dry pyridine yielded 93 c. c. methane at 25° and 766 mm.
- (b) 0.0681 g. of rauwolscine in 2 c. c. dry pyridine yielded 95 c. c. methane at 27° and 766 mm.

[Found (a) H, 0.59; (b) H, 0.596%. C₂₁H₂₃O₃N₂ requires for 2 active H, 0.57%].

Dry Distillation of Rauwolscinic Acid.—Rauwolscinic acid (2.5 g.) was heated in a metal-bath at 300° in vacuum (5 mm.). A thick brown product distilled over. The distillation was continued for half an hour when the pyrolysis was almost complete. The brown-red viscid distillate was extracted several times with ether (150 c. c. in all) and the ethereal solution (A) was shaken up with 1% hydrochloric acid (90 c. c. in 3 instalments). In this way the distillate was resolved into two fractions: (A) non-basic and (B) basic respectively.

Isolation of 3-Ethylindole from the Fraction (A).—The ethereal solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue obtained

after evaporation of ether yielded on steam-distillation, a pale yellow oil with a faecal smell. The aqueous distillate was extracted with ether when the oil passed into ethereal solution. The pale yellow ethereal extract, thus obtained, was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and ether removed. The residual brown oil distilled at $70\text{--}80^{\circ}/0\cdot1$ mm. (yield, $0\cdot1$ g.).

The oil, when freshly distilled, was practically colourless, but slowly turned brown on exposure to air. The picrate of the oil was easily obtained on treating the components in benzene, as ruby-red needles, melting at $116\text{--}22^{\circ}$. On repeated crystallisations from benzene, red glistening needles, melting at $115\text{--}16^{\circ}$, were obtained. [Found in a specimen dried in *vacuo* at 100° for 4 hours over P_2O_5 : N, 14·85. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{N} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OH} (\text{NO}_2)_3$ requires N, 14·97 per cent]. It showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with the picrate of a synthetic specimen of 3-ethylindole.

Isolation of Harman from the Fraction (B).—The well cooled, wine coloured hydrochloric acid extract, was basified with 5% sodium hydroxide solution when a semi-solid with resinous impurity separated out. It was taken up in ether and the red ethereal solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The ethereal extract was saturated with hydrochloric acid gas when a brown solid separated out. The yellow ethereal solution was decanted off and the solid mass was digested with warm water. The pale red solution was filtered from insoluble, resinous impurities, and basified with 5% sodium hydroxide solution. The base liberated was thrice subjected to the above process of purification (namely, alternate salt formation and liberation of the free base from the salts) and finally the viscous base was subjected to high vacuum distillation when a semi-crystalline product was obtained at $165\text{--}85^{\circ}/0\cdot1$ mm. This was rapidly washed with ether when the adherent oil dissolved away leaving a colourless solid residue which on redistillation in high vacuum ($165\text{--}85^{\circ}/0\cdot1$ mm.) yielded a colourless solid (0·08 g.). It crystallised from benzene as shining needles, melting at 232° . The melting point did not change when the crystals were mixed with a sample of synthetic harman. (Found in a specimen dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 4 hours at 110° : C, 79·2; H, 5·43; N, 15·40. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2$ requires C, 79·11; H, 5·5; N, 15·39 per cent). Harman, thus obtained, was found to be freely soluble in alcohol, and sparingly in benzene and difficultly in water.

The Hydrochloride of Harman.—A solution of harman (0·05 g.) in hydrochloric acid (6 c.c.) deposited on concentration (2 c.c.) shining needles of the hydrochloride melting at $276\text{--}78^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found in a specimen dried in *vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 4 hours: Cl, 16·18. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2 \cdot \text{HCl}$ requires Cl, 16·25 per cent).

The Picrate of Harman.—The picrate of harman was obtained by the usual method from an ethereal solution of the components. It melted with decomposition at 258° , and its melting point did not change when mixed with a specimen of the picrate of synthetic harman. [Found in a dry specimen: N, 17·08. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{OH} (\text{NO}_2)_3$ requires N, 17·03 per cent].

Preparation of Harman.—In synthesising harman, the method of Kermack, Perkin and Robinson was followed with a slight modification to improve the yield of the product. The tryptophan solution (0·5 g.) in water (150 c.c.) was refluxed with ice-water in the condenser for 2 hours with an aqueous solution (25%) of freshly

prepared acetaldehyde (10 c.c.) and then boiled with a 10% aqueous solution of potassium dichromate (25 c.c.) for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. Sulphur dioxide gas was bubbled through the mixture after cooling. The mixture was afterwards boiled to remove excess of sulphurous acid and treated with an aqueous solution of sodium carbonate, till faintly alkaline. The precipitate of chromium hydroxide was filtered and repeatedly washed with boiling water. The filtrate and the washings (400 c.c.) were acidified with hydrochloric acid, and concentrated (20 c.c.) and then basified with 10% aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide at 0°, when colourless flakes of harman were obtained. The flakes crystallised from benzene as lustrous needles, m.p. 232° (yield 0.40 g).

Fusion of Rauwolscinic acid with Potassium Hydroxide.—Rauwolscinic acid (2.5 g.) was fused with solid potassium hydroxide (15 g.) in a nickel crucible heated to 300° on a metal-bath. The fused mass was stirred constantly to prevent frothing of the molten mass, due to the evolution of ammonia gas. When the evolution of the gas had stopped, the mass was allowed to cool and then lixiviated with water (100 c.c.). The product was saturated with ammonium chloride to decompose excess of potassium hydroxide. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was extracted with ether. In this way ether soluble products (C) were removed.

The alkaline aqueous solution, containing acidic degradation products, was then acidified with hydrochloric acid when a pale yellow viscid mass separated and was drawn into ether. The ether solution was well washed with water and then treated with an aqueous solution of potassium hydroxide (1%). The latter was drawn out, extracted with ether to remove gummy matters and acidified with hydrochloric acid, when a viscid substance separated. This was purified by repeating the process three times. The pasty acid finally obtained was fractionally sublimed in vacuum when two fractions, (D) and (E), were obtained. Fraction D distilled at 110-115°/0.1 mm. and Fraction E at 160-180°/0.1 mm.

Isolation of Indole-2-carboxylic Acid from the Fraction (D).—The ethereal solution of the fraction (D) was repeatedly extracted with a solution of sodium bicarbonate (2*N*). The aqueous extract was cooled in ice and then acidified with hydrochloric acid. The precipitate, thus obtained, was taken up in ether. The ethereal solution was well washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The solid residue, obtained after the removal of ether, was Soxhletted with petroleum ether (50 c.c.; b.p. 30-50°) for about 8 hours, when the residue almost completely went in solution. The petroleum ether extract was concentrated to 10 c.c. and on being left overnight deposited almost colourless leaflets, m.p. 198-99°. These were further purified by crystallising first from benzene and finally from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether as shining flakes, m.p. 200-201° (yield 0.4 g.). (Found in a dry specimen: C, 67.07; H, 4.35; N, 8.7. $C_9H_7O_2N$ requires C, 67.21; H, 4.53; N, 8.87 per cent). The compound did not show any depression in melting point when mixed with a synthetic specimen of indole-2-carboxylic acid. The degradation product like indole-2-carboxylic acid gave a red-violet colouration with ßatin in concentrated sulphuric acid. On heating to 230°, it decomposed producing

an oil, which had the offensive smell of indole and which turned pine chips moistened with hydrochloric acid red.

Indole-2-carboxylic acid required for identification was prepared from 2-methylindole by fusion with caustic potash according to the method of Ciamician and Zetti (*Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1930).

Isolation of isoPhthalic Acid from the Fraction (E).—The pale yellow sublimate (obtained at 160-80°/0.1 mm.) was purified by resublimation at 310-15° at the ordinary pressure. The colourless sublimate was further purified by dissolving it in a solution of sodium bicarbonate, filtering the solution and reprecipitation by means of hydrochloric acid. It was then taken up in ether. The residue on removal of the solvent was thrice sublimed as before at 310-15°. The pure sublimate was slightly acidic to litmus and melted at 330°. It crystallised from water in shining flakes, m.p. 330° (sublimation). (Found in a specimen dried in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ for 4 hours: C, 57.65; H, 3.81. C₈H₆O₄ requires C, 57.83; H, 3.90 per cent). The acid showed no depression in melting point when mixed with synthetic *iso*phthalic acid, which was prepared by permanganate oxidation of an authentic specimen of *m*-toluic acid and which alone also melted at the same temperature.

Dimethyl Ester of the isoPhthalic Acid obtained by Potash Fusion.—The methyl ester was prepared by treating an ethereal solution of the acid (0.006 g.) with diazomethane in ether. The residue after removal of ether was an oil which distilled at 90°/0.1 mm. The distillate solidified on cooling and was crystallised from petroleum ether (b. p. 50-60°) in shining needles. The methyl ester melted at 68.5°, and showed no change in m.p. when mixed with a specimen of dimethyl ester of *iso*phthalic acid which alone melted at 68.5°.

Isolation of Harman from the Ether Extract (C).—The red coloured ethereal solution, obtained from potassium hydroxide fusion products of rauwolfscinic acid, was treated with hydrochloric acid when the acid layer (F) became red and the ether layer (G) pale yellow.

1. *Treatment of the Acid Layer (F).*—The acid solution yielded a white precipitate on basification. The precipitate was extracted with ether and on removal of ether it was recovered as a semi-solid mass, from which on treatment with hydrochloric acid, straw-yellow coloured needles, melting at 278-80° (decomp.) were obtained. The needles were purified by repeated crystallisation from water. An aqueous solution of the purified product, when made ammoniacal, deposited colourless flakes, which crystallised from benzene as shining needles, m.p. 230-31°. (Found in a specimen dried in *vacuo* over P₂O₅ for 4 hours at 110°: C, 79.25; H, 5.42; N, 15.45. C₁₂H₁₀N₂ requires C, 79.00; H, 5.5; N, 15.39 per cent). They showed no depression in melting point when mixed with an authentic specimen of harman.

Picrate of the base.—The picrate was obtained by the method previously described and had m.p. 258°, (decomp.). [Found in a dry specimen: N, 17.1. C₁₂H₁₀N₂. C₇H₅OH(NO₂)₃ requires, N, 17.03 per cent].

2. *Treatment of the ether layer (G).*—The oily residue (0.005 g.) obtained after the removal of ether had an indole-like faecal odour, and responded to the tests of an indole (pine chip reaction). Neither the residue nor its derivatives could be obtained in a solid state to facilitate further examinations.

The author wishes to offer her best thanks to Dr. P. K. Bose for his keen interest and the facilities given, and to Mr. N. Ghosh, MSc. for the microanalyses.

Received September 16, 1942.

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COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH BIVALENT METALS. PART IV. PALLADIUM BIGUANIDINE AND ITS SALTS

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Palladium is known to resemble nickel in many of its chemical properties and possesses like the latter an electronic structure of the pseudo-inert gas type. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to study the preparation and properties of palladium biguanide complexes and compare them with those of nickel. Besides palladium biguanidine and its hydroxide, a number of other salts, namely, chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, thiosulphate, thiocyanate, nitrate, palladothiocyanate, chloropalladite and chloroplatinate have been described in this paper. The palladium biguanide complex resembles the corresponding nickel complex, but is more stable and comparatively less soluble. The complex thiocyanate undergoes an interesting disproportionation in presence of acid to form palladium biguanidinium palladothiocyanate.

In parts I and II of this series, copper and nickel biguanidines and their salts have been described (Ray and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 617; Ray and Purakayastha, *ibid.*, 1941, 18, 217). As nickel and palladium resemble each other in many of their chemical properties and possess an electronic structure of pseudo-inert gas type, it was naturally expected that complex palladium biguanide compounds, similar to those of nickel, could be readily obtained. The present paper deals with the preparation and properties of these compounds. Besides palladium biguanidine and its hydroxides, a number of palladium biguanidinium salts, *viz.*, chloride, bromide, iodide, sulphate, thiosulphate, nitrate, thiocyanate, palladothiocyanate, chloropalladite and chloroplatinate, have been prepared. Their solubility and other properties follow the corresponding nickel compounds, but are somewhat more intensified regarding their complex character. In other words, the palladium complexes are relatively more stable and less soluble than their nickel analogues. The palladium biguanide complex is light yellow in colour and diamagnetic. Hence, like the corresponding nickel complex it is believed to possess a planar configuration with dsp^2 hybrid bonds.